

Formulation and Evaluation of Herbal Neem Face Wash

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Abstract

Azadirachta indica, which is also referred to as neem, is well known for its medicinal value and is used around the world. Products obtained from Azadirachta indica contain a number of useful characteristics like antibacterial, antifungal, and antioxidant properties. Natural products are mostly used because they are perceived to be safer with less side effect compared to synthetical alternatives. As a result, there is an increasing need for herbal products in the international market. In this study, we set out to develop and assess a herbal anti-acne face wash using an aqueous neem leaf extract (Azadirachta indica). Unlike most of the topical herbal products used for treating acne that can include synthetic products, we seek to develop a completely herbal product.

Several investigations have documented the antimicrobial, antioxidant, and anti-inflammatory activity of plants to form a sound base for this project. The prepared face wash was subjected to thorough evaluation in terms of color, appearance, consistency, pH, stability, and acceptability by consumers. Results reveal that the face wash is non-irritating, stable, and shows anti-acne activity. In comparison with a reference polyherbal gel, its activity was found to be almost comparable.

Keywords: Azadirachta; Antibacterial; Antifungal; Antioxidant; Non-Irritating; Polyherbal Gel

1. Introduction

Azadirachta indica or Neem, of the family Meliaceae, has been in use in Ayurvedic practices for centuries. The medicinal values of various parts of the Neem tree are well known and are often used by Ayurvedic, Siddha, and herbal medicine practitioners in India. Neem leaves have a vast range of characteristics such as antibacterial, anti-parasitic, anti-inflammatory, and antioxidant activities. Its widespread application in traditional medicine is an indication of its effectiveness in treating a wide range of health problems. Neem, which originates in India, occurs naturally in tropical and subtropical areas of various nations. Its extensive coverage testifies to its immense medicinal importance. Chemical compounds isolated from Neem, including alkaloids, flavonoids, triterpenoids, phenolic compounds, carotenoids, steroids, and ketones, are rich in various biologically active compounds. Other notable compounds present in Azadirachta indica such as salannin, volatile oils, meliantriol, and nimbin, responsible for its biological activity. The leaves of Azadirachta indica are found to be useful in curing different skin diseases like eczema, ringworm, and acne, due to their anti-inflammatory and antihyperglycemic activities. They are also used in the healing of chronic wounds, diabetic symptom management, and treating ailments such as gangrene. Neem is supposed to help detoxify, neutralize free radicals, and clean the blood.

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1.1. Vernacular names of plant

- Hindi–Neem
- Marathi -Kadunimb
- English -Margosa, Neem, Indian Lilac

1.2. Medicinal Properties

- Antibacterial Compounds: Neem exhibits antibacterial activity in oral health, gum disease, cavities, and as a vaginal contraceptive.
- Antifungal Properties: Neem demonstrates efficacy against fungi causing conditions like athlete's foot, ringworm, and Candida infections.
- Diseases, eye issues, age-related neurodegeneration, and cancer by boosting antioxidant levels.
- Antiviral Compounds: Neem inhibits viruses like Dengue and coxsackie B virus, which causes various infections in humans.
- Conditions like psoriasis, eczema, and persistent infections.

1.3. Therapeutic Applications

- Addressing scalp issues like dandruff, itchiness, and scalp conditions.
- Managing acne.
- Alleviating symptoms of skin disorders such as eczema and psoriasis.
- Facilitating wound healing processes.
- Treating fungal infections, ringworm, infected sores, and burns.
- Managing athlete's foot.
- Treating nail fungus and restoring fragile nails.
- A facial cleanser is a crucial skincare product designed to eliminate makeup, dead skin cells, oil, dirt, and various pollutants from the facial skin, aiding in unclogging pores and preventing acne and other skin conditions. Typically, it is part of a skincare routine alongside a toner and moisturizer.

1.4. Advantages of Using Face Wash

- Facilitates the removal of dead skin cells, allowing for the regeneration of new skin cells.
- Promotes a fresh and healthy complexion, imparting radiance to the skin.
- Helps prevent acne, whiteheads, blackheads, and dullness by clearing pores and eliminating excess oil.
- Regular exfoliation reduces the formation of wrinkles by removing dead skin cells, slowing down the aging process.

1.5. Properties of Face Wash

- Accelerates blood circulation and stimulates skin regeneration and rejuvenation through exfoliation.

- Effectively cleanses facial pores and reduces oil buildup in oily skin, often caused by excessive sebum secretion.
- Herbal face washes, enriched with botanicals like neem, are renowned for treating acne and pimples without stripping the skin of its nutrients.
- After water evaporation, the residue left behind should not become thick or viscous.

1.6. Uses of Face Wash

- Daily removal of makeup residue.
- Cleansing the skin thoroughly.
- Aiding in anti-aging efforts.

2. Preparation Methods of Neem Leaf Extracts (nles):

2.1. Plant Material Selection and Collection

Choosing disease-free and healthy plants is crucial for efficient phytoconstituent isolation. Plants should be protected from weeds and insects during collection.

2.2. Plant Material Drying

The drying process is essential for extracting plant materials. Fresh plant materials contain active enzymes that facilitate the production of active constituents and metabolic reactions.

Air drying in shaded, dark rooms is commonly employed to prevent loss of volatile substances and light-sensitive constituents. Other drying methods such as microwave drying, oven drying, silica gel or salt drying, and freeze drying are also utilized.

2.3. Grinding and Size Reduction

Grinding and size reduction are necessary for the soxhlet extraction process as smaller particle sizes increase the surface area of powdered particles, enhancing contact with the extraction solvent.

Various methods such as hammer mills, fixed head mills, plate mills, roller mills, and cutter mills are used for size reduction.

2.4. Size Separation/Sieving

Uniform particle size is important for efficient soxhlet extraction, ensuring maximum extraction efficiency as the solvent can uniformly pass through the powdered particles. Size separation is achieved through sieving

3. Methods to determine particle size

3.1. Solvent Selection for Soxhlet Extraction

Solvent selection for soxhlet extraction is based on the phytoconstituent isolation process. Solvents should be easily removable and inert. Selection is typically based on increasing polarity order, with options including acetone, petroleum ether, ethyl acetate, chloroform, methanol, ethanol, and water. Ethanol, a semi-polar solvent, is commonly used for extracting many phytoconstituents, while water, a polar solvent, is cost-effective and non-toxic.

3.2. Extraction Process

Following soxhlet extraction, extracted materials undergo post-extraction processes such as concentrate extraction, solvent evaporation, and extract storage.

Distillation processes or various evaporators are employed to isolate extracts from solvents. Rotary evaporators and distillation methods are commonly used and air drying may also be utilized for concentrate extraction. Extracts are stored in well-sealed containers covered with aluminum foil and stored in refrigerators.

4. Preparation Procedure for Neem Face Wash

- Carbopol 934 was dispersed in distilled water to form a gel by allowing it to swell, and the mixture was set aside.
- Distilled water and the appropriate amount of neem oil were heated on a water bath until completely dissolved. After cooling, propylene glycol 400 and sodium lauryl sulfate were incorporated into the solution.
- The specified quantity of neem extract was introduced into the mixture. This solution was then combined with the Carbopol 940 gel under continuous stirring. Triethanolamine was added gradually to regulate the skin's pH and attain the desired gel consistency.

5. Formulation table for neem face wash

Table 1 Formulation Table

Sr. No.	Name of Ingredients	Properties	Formulation Weight
1	Ethanollic neem extract	Anti-Microbial, anti-oxidant	2.5ml
2	Carbopol 934	Gelling agent	0.83gm
3	Triethanolamine	Neutralizer	0.2ml
4	Propylene glycol	Humectant	0.1ml
5	Neem oil	Preservative	1ml
6	Sodium lauryl sulphate (SLS)	Foaming agent	1.66gm
7	Distilled water	Vehicle	50ml

6. Phytochemical analysis of azadirachta indica

Table 2 Phytochemical Analysis

Sr. no.	Test	Procedure	Observation
1	Test for alkaloids	2ml of plant extract + few drop of wagner's solution	Brown, reddish precipitates
2	Test for Flavonoids	2ml of plant extract + 1ml of 2M NaOH	Yellow colour shows
3	Test for cardiac glycosides	2ml of plant extract + few drop of conc H ₂ SO ₄	Formation of red colour
4	Test for amino acid	2ml plant extract + drops of ninhydrine solution. Sample kept in boiling water for 1-2 min	Purpl colour appear
5	Test for tannins	2ml of plant extract + 2 drop of ferric chloride	Yellow colour appear
6	Test for reducing sugar	2ml of plant extract + 2ml fehling's solution sample kept in water bath	Brick red precipitation
7	Test for steroids	1ml plant extract + 2 ml acetic anhydride & 2-3 drop chloroform + 2 drop conc H ₂ SO ₄	Blue/ orange colour appear
8	Test for phenols	2ml plant extract + few drop of aqueous ferric chloride solution	Blue/ green colour appear
9	Test for saponins	2ml plant extract + 2ml distilled water shake vigorously	Foam appears on top of sample
10	Test for carbohydrate	1ml plant extract + drops of molish reagent + 1ml conc sulphuric acid	Red/ violet colour appear

7. Evaluation Parameters

- Colour: yellowish white
 - pH: 5.0-6.0
 - Odour: herbal, slightly medicinal scent
 - Consistency: semi-solid gel
 - Washability: rinses with water
 - Foamability: depend on combined ingredient
 - Viscosity:1520cPs
 - Irritancy test: no irritation
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8. Result

Reviews for herbal Neem face washes generally highlight their effectiveness in treating acne, reducing oiliness, and improving overall skin freshness. Many users report that these products are gentle and non-drying, making them suitable for acne-prone and oily skin types. Common benefits include a reduction in pimples and dark spots, and a smoother, refreshed feeling after use.

9. Conclusion

This study indicates that the Gentle Neem Face Wash is quite safe and efficacious. It corrects common dermatological problems in like reduction in oiliness of facial skin and minimizing the recurrence of acne. It has not produced any adverse effect.

Compliance with ethical standards

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Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest to be disclosed.

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